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Adrenogenital syndrome

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Annatsiya. Adrenogenital syndrome-hereditary disease of the adrenal glands, here to solve the functional guarantee of the enzyme and the disabled due to steroidogenesis break. During diagnostic 17-gidroksiprogesteron, 17-ketosteroidlar, androstenedion, ACTH levels, ultrasound of the ovaries controller. Glyukokortikoidlar and mineralokortikoidlar patients with hormone replacement, androgen, or estrogen is prescribed in conjunction with the new generation of progestinlari. Keep it simple and to fail vir Soltering the main clinical forms of the disease virilizatsiyasi antenatal genital organs visible sign. There are signs pseudohermafroditizm women in new born babies. Clitoris the size of a large cone-shaped or has a form, the enhancement of the mouth of the vagina, genitourinary sinus is formed, and the expansion of small city big lips, perineum tall. Internal normally developed sexual organs.

Keywords: Adrenogenital syndrome, genitourinary sinuses, lips, large and small, the expansion of the city, pseudohermafroditizm.

The relevance of the topic of: Adrenogenital syndrome - the face of corticosteroids caused by congenital defects of the enzymes necessary for clinical

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biosintezi that gives a sim-ptomlar set. Po'st of the floor to him virilizatsiya congenital adrenal gland-hyperplasia of the official delegations would cause for servicing. Virilizatsiyalovchi Adrenogenital syndrome in almost the same amount of cortisol in the blood at low doses, increased androgen is going. The son of the external members of this girl sex of the fetus, the fetus will be specific to. Virilizatsiya takes after the birth of a daughter, gavin male structure is similar, the milk glands do not grow and does not see menses. The son of a fetus after the birth of five members of the minor child sex quickly develops and reaches in advance. Adrenogenital syndrome caused by loss of salt cortisol and aldosteron arising from different meta-bolizmida much deeper changes observed is typical. The amount of this hormone is too low, the patient gives the shortage of ruy po'st the adrenal gland in the floor. Cha-aluq fake xunasalik symptoms, degidratatsiyasi the body (as a result of sodium loss), later the heart-the sudden cessation of cardiac activity is observed and the shortage of vessels children die as a result of it. Adrenaline korteksning konjenital disfunktsiyasi or adrenogenital syndrome (giperplaziya) inherited in most of the disease occurs. The spread of pathology between the representatives of different nations makes a difference. Classic version of the caucasus people in the ag's 1:14 000 frequency occurs in infants, Alaska eskimos, while this figure 1:282. Of the jews, the incidence is much higher. So, adrenogenital disorders in the ashkenazi jewish group of those who belongs to the nation with the classic form of 19% to be determined. Autosoma at retsessiv depending on the type of pathology is transmitted. Such a pathological syndrome in the carriage of the gene of both parents with the birth of a child, the probability of 25%, in the life of the patient

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and the carrier-75%. One of the parents is full of you if you have the dna, the contours of the syndrome in children is not administered in clinical development. You the father and the mother, the child is too sick. The characteristic of the genital organs, which is able to change the type of the ag is not difficult immediately after birth and antenatal diagnosis is performed. In questionable cases karyotiplash karyotipini woman (46XH), molecular-genetic testing is used to confirm. External contours with minimal clinical or diagnostic debut later virilizatsiyaning the importance of the secret search with the flow. Laboratory and instrumental methods for the detection of adrenogenital syndrome in such cases apply.

Pathogenesis: 21 CYP-B-adrenogenital syndrome with defects of the gene to produce a mechanism for the most common version of the basis of the principle of feedback. Its first communication steroid cortisol and the lack of aldosteronning. 17-deoksikortizol and deoksikortikosteronga 11-full gidroksiprogesteron and progesterone and the disabled, along with the guarantee of the transition period prescribed by gidroksilatsiya process are observed. As a result, this process reduced the secretion of cortisol is the pituitary gland to stimulate the production of adrenaline and corticosteroids to cover bring it increases the synthesis of the hormone acth korteksning kompensatsion hiperplaziyasiga. Alternatively, increases the synthesis of androgen-sensitive and clear signs of their effects on tissues and organs appear. Kortikoid administered with a moderate decrease of enzymes active in the development of mineral failure because it is not almost 200-fold lower than kortizolga aldosteronga needs. 've only gene, which manifests itself at an early age leads to serious clinical signs of deep

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defects.

Adrenogenital syndrome treatment: The basic method of the adrenal gland vir keep the correct disfunktsiyasini to fail-which eliminates the failure glyukokortikoidlar hormone replacement therapy. The female reproductive ag which is the hidden plan, the monthly giperandrogeniyaning the contours of the skin and insignificant found a rhythm, hormones are not used. In other cases, the mode of treatment to select to the shape of endocrine pathology, depends on the level of the leading character, and his violence. Often the drug is selected according to certain other medicines glyukokortikoidlar therapeutic and surgical methods for the purpose of the appointment is filled with.

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